

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE REGULARITIES OF FORMATION OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK TERMS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of linguistic terms in the Uzbek and English languages, in which the aim was to provide a comparative description of the laws and requirements for the formation of terms. The research and opinions of terminologists in this area were studied. The differences in the formation of linguistic terms were analyzed through linguistic dictionaries in two languages. From the comparative analysis, we can see that while English terminology is rich in abbreviations, the Uzbek language is distinguished by its exception. While the adaptation and nationalization of terms to the language play an important role according to Uzbek terminological requirements, English terminology differs in the creation of new words and its basis in international standards. It should not be forgotten that the differences in the formation of terms are also related to the vocabulary and linguistic laws of the language. This is of great importance in the development of a terminological corpus and the development of a terminological base.

Key words: linguistics, term, terminology, linguistics, standardization, terminological corpus, standardization.

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Ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi.

Farg'ona Shahar, O'zbekiston.

In the process of scientific development, the formation of new concepts and scientific terms is increasing. In the field of linguistics, there are also specific rules for the formation of terms in this field. Therefore, the goal was to study English and Uzbek terms in a comparative form, and linguistic terminological dictionaries were taken as a source. Although a number of studies have been conducted in this area, a comparative analysis of the laws of formation of terms in English and Uzbek has not been studied sufficiently. In particular, the differences that arise in the processes of abbreviations, assimilation, adaptation and nationalization have not been fully covered from a scientific point of view. The results of the study are of practical importance in clarifying the relationship between Uzbek and English terminology, finding equivalent options in the translation process, and enriching the terminological base (Dadaboyev,2009:59). This study used comparative and descriptive methods. Through the comparative method, the regularities of term formation in English and Uzbek were compared, their similarities and differences were identified. Using the descriptive method, the mechanisms of term formation - the processes of assimilation, adaptation, abbreviation, nationalization and semantic expansion - were linguistically analyzed.

Also, the content analysis method was used to create a terminological corpus, and terms were collected based on English and Uzbek sources and grouped structurally. The most commonly used formation methods were identified through statistical calculations. During the study, the regularities of term formation in English and Uzbek were studied. The analysis showed that English terminology develops mainly through abbreviation, composition, neologization and the use of international elements (Greco-Latin morphemes). This indicates the dynamic development of the English language on a global scale and its adaptability to scientific and technical progress.

From the point of view of terminology theory, linguistic criteria [1] play an important role in the process of linking concepts with terms. The rules established in the International Terminology Standard are directly consistent with the linguistic dimension of terminology, and we can see that terms are formed subject to the following requirements:

1. Linguistic appropriateness (semantic appropriateness).

Terms must meet the requirements of semantic accuracy and denotative appropriateness. In other words, polysemy should not be allowed when choosing a term, it must clearly express the denotate (the designated object or concept). For example, the distinction between the terms “morpheme” and “affix” presents a problem of semantic ambiguity and false connotation. Confusing morpheme with affix creates semantic ambiguity.

2. Linguistic economy.

The principle of brevity is important in terminology. Excessively long terms reduce efficiency in pragmatics. For example, the form “term bank” corresponds to the law of economy in the naming act, while the “terminological data bank” is superfluous and is considered a redundant unit. This principle can be said to be one of the main problems in the creation of Uzbek terminology. For example, word formation is translated as the process of word formation and does not obey the laws of terminological linguistic economy.

3. Derivability. In the selection of terms, their word-formation potential is of great importance. This aspect expands the derivational paradigm of the term and ensures its systematicity. Morphology, morphemic analysis and morphemic derivatives have arisen from the basis of morphemes, and have the potential to create many more derivatives. This fully corresponds to the principle of terminological systematicity. Also, the analysis of the existing scientific literature shows that the lexical terminology of the English language is studied more on the basis of the comparative method, that is, in comparison with the Russian linguistic terminology. This creates certain gaps in the full coverage of the independent terminological system of the English language.

In this regard, a systematic study of English lexical terminology in terms of form and content, for example: “polysemy - polysemy”, “homonymy - similar words”, “synonymy - synonymy”, etc. It is noted that in modern English, abbreviation is one of the most active neologism-forming methods. Because abbreviations simultaneously provide two main functions of the term - brevity and semantic completeness. including UFO (unidentified flying objects), AI (artificial intelligence), IT (information technology), etc.

With the development of new technologies and production processes, new terms appear, existing ones are updated, and the process of terminology continues. This process leads to the widespread distribution of neologisms, including abbreviations. In the 21st century, abbreviation is the most active way of word formation. Because abbreviations help to quickly

and effectively convey information. Their widespread distribution in many areas, including general lexicon and terminology, is associated with socio-economic, political and cultural factors of society.

Currently, a “terminological explosion” is being observed. This means not only the creation of new units, but also the assignment of new terminological meanings to existing words. An ordinary word or combination is used as a term to denote a new object for a specific communication need. This is called functional reorientation

Terminologists also have their own views on the laws of term formation, and they have emphasized that terms can be created based on specific ideas and rules. The scientific validity of terms and the possibility of their practical application are considered the most important criteria of the science of terminology. As Vakulenko (1996:183) noted, the viability of a term is determined not by personal preferences or subjective views, but by its relevance, which is determined by scientific validity and statistical methods.

Uzbek terminology is more dependent on the processes of adaptation, semantic adaptation, assimilation and nationalization. This, in turn, is closely related to historical development, the influence of other languages, and translation processes. According to the results of comparative analysis, short and concise terms prevail in English. For example, we can cite CVC-consonant-vowel-consonant (consonant-vowel-consonant), SVO - subject-verb-object (possessor-objective)

The results show that identifying the similarities and differences in the processes of terminology formation in English and Uzbek is not only of theoretical importance, but also of importance in translation studies and practical terminology.

The research of the Russian linguist I.V. Motchenko analyzed English terminology according to its lexical, semantic, morphological and etymological aspects. According to him, modern English terms are formed by such methods as abbreviation, affixation, conversion, metaphorization, metonymization, synonymy, and terminization. According to his research, linguistic terms were formed according to the following factors:

- scientific and technological revolution;
- new directions in the field of linguistics;
- new social phenomena.

If we pay attention to English linguistic dictionaries, scientists began to work on them from the 19th century. The first linguistic dictionary was created by Mario A. Pei and Frank Gaynor. According to the author's explanation, it did not include expressions that are widely used in linguistics. For example, alphabet-alifbo, word-formation- so'z yasalishi, etc. The dictionary created by David Crystal (2006:312) differs in that the terms are taken from a broad perspective and their relationship to other disciplines is also studied.

In conclusion, we can say that, despite the fact that the rules for forming terms are standardized all over the world, each language differs in its own uniqueness, based on its own historical and linguistic experiences. That is, while Uzbek terminology adheres to a system that preserves national identity, is free from polysemy, and adheres to linguistic economy, English terminology is distinguished by the uniqueness of a terminological system based on international standards and rich in abbreviations.

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